

Unplanned Use of Schools as Emergency Temporary Camps for Displaced Disaster Victims: Implications for Teaching and Learning Outcomes in Nigeria

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Abstract

When schools are inundated and submerged by floods, overwhelmed with extreme drought and heatwaves, lockdown by persistent conflicts crises and banditry, or sudden epidemics like the case of COVID-19 and Ebola, etc, academic activities are disrupted, causing a significant impact on students' learning. Classrooms and educational materials may be damaged or destroyed, leading to school closure and suspension of formal teaching and learning. This paper therefore evaluates the Unplanned Use of Schools as Emergency Temporary Camps for Displaced Disaster Victims and its Implications for Teaching and Learning Outcomes in Nigeria. Its specific objectives were to assess the rationale for designating school facilities as emergency temporary camps during and after a disaster; the effect of unplanned school closure on the children, teachers or staff, parents or family, as well as the school academic calendar; and the key considerations and checklist for preparing schools as temporary camps for displaced disaster victims. The paper noted the absence of adequate preparedness plans, a lack of resilient school infrastructure, a low level of deployment of digital teaching and learning platforms, as well as other adaptive and contingency measures as some of the limitations in the use of schools as temporary camps for disaster evacuees and victims prepared and planned well ahead before a disaster strike. It recommends deploying a new paradigm shift of having adequate contingency planning and preparedness in place before a disaster strikes, in a bid to mitigate the impact of the disruption of already planned school academic calendar and activities, thereby ensuring that formal teaching and learning are minimally disrupted most especially in the Secondary and Primary Schools which are the ones that are regularly used as as temporary camps for disaster displaced victims in Nigeria.

Keywords: *school closure, displaced victims, disaster, unplanned, camps.*

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Introduction

In recent decades, schools around the world have frequently been repurposed—often

without prior planning—as temporary or even long-term shelters for students, their families, and internally displaced populations during

times of crisis (Anderson et al., 2017). Additionally, in conflict zones, educational facilities have sometimes been taken over by armed groups, leading to major disruptions in schooling, physical damage to school infrastructure and resources, and exposing children to heightened risks of abuse, neglect, and exploitation (Anderson et al., 2017).

Beyond the interruption of scheduled academic programs and institutional plans, teachers have also encountered significant obstacles in fulfilling their professional responsibilities (Kawasaki et al., 2021). Among these duties is the critical task of safeguarding students throughout the school day. However, in schools converted into evacuation shelters, educators often find themselves unexpectedly reassigned to administrative roles within the shelter operations while still being expected to continue educational activities for the children (Kawasaki et al., 2021).

Several studies have highlighted parental concerns regarding the transformation of their children's schools into shelters for individuals affected by disasters (Anderson, et al., 2017). In a survey examining these concerns, parents reported various issues tied to the use of educational facilities as temporary refuge spaces. Their responses indicated worries about the unreliable and insufficient availability of basic daily needs; the strain on social relationships caused by difficult evacuation procedures; and the lack of privacy when living in close quarters with familiar people. They also described the shelter environment as mentally taxing—overcrowded, poorly ventilated, and emotionally draining. Additional concerns included inadequate management of shelter conditions and the heightened risk of unsanitary living situations (Kawasaki et al., 2021). According to Anderson et al. (2017), such concerns have prompted both policymakers and humanitarian professionals to call for clearer guidelines on the matter. Considering the vital role education plays during emergencies, the prolonged use of schools as shelters—or worse, their occupation by armed groups—should be considered unacceptable under any circumstances.

Very pronounced concerns of parents border on how the Children cannot continue studying when displaced from their schools to give way for evacuees from a disaster. Some of the direct responses to the survey of some concerns raised by parents conducted by Kawasaki, et al, (2021) include:

- *"What happens to the children's education if the classrooms are also made open to evacuees?"*
- *"I want to avoid sacrificing my child's learning and activities for a long period."*
- *"I am worried about a decline in my child's academic ability and advancement to the next educational tier due to their inability to study."*
- *"I think a school is the place to raise the spirits (of children) that have dropped. Due to the disaster. I am worried, that this venue will be unavailable for a long time.", etc.*

According to Erica, et al (2018), Flooding-related displacement puts children in disaster areas at a disadvantage academically at the important school age, which prepares them for future economic disadvantage and chances. There is proof that overall educational performances and results are worse, educational levels are lower, and general disadvantages persist throughout adulthood (Erica, et al, 2018). In areas with already insufficient access to education, the consequences of flooding catastrophes on the educational sector are especially detrimental. In the worst-hit developing countries, efforts to restore destroyed schools are typically postponed. Young schoolchildren who live in places that often experience floods on a scale not considered a catastrophic disaster lose many months of the academic year each year, which has a much more significant impact on their education (Lawal, et al, 2024).

In Nigeria, flooding remains the most persistent and widespread natural disaster, frequently causing extensive destruction to residential structures and essential infrastructure, thereby displacing individuals from their homes and forcing them to seek refuge in temporary shelters (Geng et al., 2012; Tsioulou et al., 2021). Although flooding affects various regions across

the nation, schools in Nigeria are also vulnerable to additional hazards such as drought, extreme heat, armed banditry, and violent conflicts—risks that are particularly concentrated in the northern part of the country. While severe floods have prompted government-mandated school closures in several areas, ongoing security threats such as kidnapping, insurgency, and banditry have also led to the suspension of educational activities in certain northern states. Given the significant number of people typically displaced during such crises, establishing emergency evacuation procedures and temporary accommodation is a critical element that must be integrated into a broader disaster preparedness, mitigation, and response strategy (Geng et al., 2012).

Regrettably, in the absence of prior contingency planning and adequate preparedness for accommodating potential internally displaced persons (IDPs), schools—which are fundamentally intended for educational purposes and constructed in line with institutional standards—are often abruptly repurposed as temporary shelters. This unplanned shift places significant strain on these facilities and subjects them to numerous operational challenges and disruptions (Geng et al., 2012). Even though, Nigeria's national policy on Education ought to have captured the need for adequate contingency planning and preparedness for disaster, despite the constant use of schools to serve as temporary shelters for flood disasters and insurgency crises across the country. The implications are already far-reaching on the school system in Nigeria, thereby necessitating the inclusion of school contingency planning and preparedness against disaster in the education policy going forward. For instance, Schools in Nigeria are unable to fulfill their core educational function because they act as emergency shelters during natural calamities like flooding or man-made calamities like conflicts crises, banditry and kidnapping. In areas with already insufficient access to education, the consequences of these catastrophes on the educational sector are usually detrimental (Geng, et al 2012 & Lawal, et al 2024).

It is in light of the foregoing that this paper assessed the Unplanned Use of Schools as Emergency Temporary Camps for Displaced Disaster Victims and its Implications for Teaching and Learning Outcomes in Nigeria. Its specific objectives were to assess the rationale for designating school facilities as emergency temporary camps during and after a disaster; the effect of unplanned school closure on the children, teachers or staff, parents or family, as well as the school academic calendar; and the key considerations and checklist for preparing schools as temporary camps for displaced disaster victims. It thus brings to the fore the need to explore and deploy a new paradigm shift of having adequate planning and preparedness in place before a disaster strikes. The expected outcome is to forestall and mitigate the impact of sudden disruption of the school system, with particular reference to the Secondary and Primary Schools which are the ones that are regularly used as temporary shelters for disaster-displaced victims in Nigeria.

Conceptual Clarifications

The School System

The concept of a "school" is generally understood as an establishment dedicated to the process of teaching and learning, created with the core objective of delivering formal education (Rahmatullah et al., 2022). More specifically, it can be defined as both an institution and a structured educational system that facilitates the transmission of socially sanctioned knowledge through an officially recognized curriculum and teaching approach. This system typically involves trained and salaried educators, mandatory student attendance, and organized class groupings (Burke & Grosvenor, 2008). In essence, schools are purpose-built institutions that structure and institutionalize the educational experience.

In the United States, particularly in North America, the term "school" encompasses a wide range of educational levels, including early childhood education such as preschool and kindergarten, as well as elementary, middle (also known as intermediate or junior high), high school, and further extending to post-secondary

institutions like colleges, universities, and graduate schools (Sheu et al., 2014).

Conversely, in the United Kingdom, the term predominantly refers to institutions that cater to learners before they enter higher education. These include nursery or pre-schools, primary schools (sometimes subdivided into infant and junior schools), and secondary schools (Burke & Grosvenor, 2008). A similar interpretation is observed across many Commonwealth countries such as Australia, New Zealand, India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, South Africa, Kenya, and Tanzania, where "school" primarily denotes pre-tertiary education institutions.

In the Nigerian context, however, Mark (2024) notes that the term is used in a broader sense, encompassing not only nursery and primary schools but also secondary and tertiary institutions. This paper, however, narrows its scope to focus exclusively on primary and secondary schools—both public and private—as these are the types of institutions most commonly repurposed as temporary shelters for individuals displaced by disasters, widely recognized as Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs).

Emergency Closure of the School System

Ewing (2021) defines the "school system" within the field of education as the coordinated framework responsible for delivering educational services across all stages—from early childhood education to tertiary institutions—alongside essential support structures. This system encompasses the governance, policy frameworks, financial mechanisms, and material resources necessary to facilitate learning and personal development.

A school closure, in this context, refers to the sudden and unexpected shutdown of a school during an academic session, which disrupts students' progress by preventing them from completing their coursework or earning academic credit. In contrast, an emergency school closure implies a temporary halt in regular school operations due to unforeseen events that compromise the safety or feasibility of continuing instruction. Such interruptions may arise from extreme weather conditions, health

crises, or other disruptions impacting the school environment.

In Nigeria, for example, common causes of abrupt school system shutdowns include large-scale flooding, outbreaks of disease, and growing threats of insecurity such as kidnapping and armed banditry.

Emergency Camps or Shelters after a Disaster

An emergency shelter or camp represents more than just a physical structure like a building or tent—it serves as a protective space for individuals who have been displaced, either temporarily or permanently, due to a disaster that has rendered their normal living conditions uninhabitable (Chaudhary, et al 2024). The UNHCR (2024) emphasizes that providing shelter in emergency situations is a core, life-saving obligation of humanitarian agencies, ensuring that those who are forcibly displaced have access to a safe, healthy environment. Such shelter must safeguard individuals from harsh weather, while also offering essential elements like privacy, dignity, comfort, and emotional well-being (UNHCR, 2024).

Emergency shelters, therefore, function as secure locations for evacuation, providing refuge for affected individuals and serving as operational hubs for coordinating disaster response efforts (Kılıç, 2015). As such, their provision is a vital aspect of comprehensive emergency management strategies. Elements such as the design, location, construction standards, and surrounding environment of these temporary shelters are all considered critical in enhancing the resilience and disaster preparedness of communities, municipalities, or entire regions (Geng, et al. 2021).

Disaster Contingency Plan or Planning for Schools

Contingency planning refers to the proactive process of preparing an organization to respond swiftly and effectively when emergencies or disasters occur. Its core objective is to ensure readiness through established systems and actionable strategies that allow for a rapid and organized response once a crisis unfolds (IFRC, 2012, 2021). This approach involves foreseeing

possible types of disasters and developing practical mechanisms to handle them efficiently. As such, contingency planning is carried out ahead of time to ensure preparedness, reflecting the widely used expression: "Time invested in contingency planning is time saved during a disaster."

Implementing a comprehensive disaster contingency plan within schools is especially vital for protecting students—one of the most vulnerable segments of society during emergencies. Children are often disproportionately affected when disasters occur, and ensuring their safety requires structured, anticipatory planning. A clear example is Nigeria's recurring floods, which frequently disrupt the education system. Although disaster response and recovery efforts aim to reduce immediate impacts and restore normalcy after a crisis, their effectiveness significantly depends on the existence of well-developed preparedness and contingency strategies established prior to the disaster event.

Schools Vulnerability

Vulnerability refers to the attributes and conditions—whether physical, social, economic, or environmental—that heighten the likelihood of individuals, communities, assets, or systems being adversely affected by hazardous events (UNDRR, 2017). Vulnerability, coming from the Latin word for "wound," (*vulnus*), also refers to the quality of being easily hurt or attacked or the state of being open to injury. This explains why children in some schools are usually more vulnerable to disaster exposure and impacts than those in other schools or locations, hence the need to always have a preparedness plan in place to mitigate the effect and lessen the number of school children, staff and parents that may be vulnerable when a disaster strikes during a school session.

According to the *No Child Left Behind Report* (2020), vulnerable children are defined as those who face an increased likelihood of physical or emotional harm and/or poor developmental outcomes due to certain risk factors present in their lives. These children may come from diverse backgrounds and carry varied personal histories, which can significantly influence their

emotional well-being, cognitive development, capacity for forming secure attachments, and ability to engage in learning (Welch, 2021). This underscores the point that when a disaster occurs, it does not affect schools in isolation—the entire school community, including students, teachers, and even parents arriving with their children, may be directly impacted by the event. Therefore, understanding the levels of vulnerability and exposure within a school environment is key to recognizing why some relatively moderate hazards can result in severe consequences, while more intense events might not lead to disaster (Chatterjee, 2017).

Rationale and Key Considerations / Checklist for Preparing Schools as Temporary Camps / Shelters for Disaster Victims

Quite often, and despite this controversy, school premises and buildings are designated or assigned as emergency evacuation shelters, temporary accommodations as well as relief material distribution hubs after a disaster. However desirable or suitable it may seem to be, in the short or long time, there has been a serious contest over the use of school facilities for different purposes aside from teaching and learning. Dela Cruz (2017) highlights that utilizing schools as emergency shelters offers several advantages, such as ample space and essential resources like electricity, water, and restroom facilities. Additionally, Raptor (2023) points out that the community's existing familiarity with the school environment can help minimize uncertainty and stress during crises. Moreover, involving school administrators in leading the coordination efforts can facilitate smoother collaboration with local emergency response teams.

In the states of Texas and Florida in the United States for instance, Raptor (2023) further noted that there are legislation and laws to adopt public school resources to play a critical role in protecting the life and well-being of disaster victims in catastrophic conditions. Given the experiences of Japan with Disasters and the management of victims, it is now an official policy of the government of Japan to integrate

the use of schools as shelters in the event of a disaster. (Kruger, et al, 2019; Cabinet Office, Government of Japan, 2019; UNHCR, 2024). In several African countries, Schools are often used as temporary emergency camps for disaster-displaced victims due to their readily available structure, capacity, accessibility, cost-effective shelter solutions, and providing a sense of normalcy and continuity for displaced children during crises.

Similarly, in Nigeria, a report by UNICEF (2021) noted that Schools are frequently used as temporary shelters for disaster-displaced victims due to their accessibility, familiarity, and potential to provide basic needs like shelter, water, and sanitation. They are often perceived as safe, child-friendly spaces and community hubs, making them a natural gathering point for displaced individuals seeking refuge, in some cases, some of these schools are sometimes designed to be more resilient structures, offering temporary protection and shelters for those that may have been displaced by a disaster or conflicts, and or banditry as it is often the case of Nigeria. An integrated approach to disaster management requires an effective chain of actions that are risk-informed with the ultimate of achieving resilience. This informed some countries like Japan to ensure that disaster risk management is infused into development, governance, and the school system.

In the work of Raptor (2023) on the nine (9) Considerations for Planning to Use Schools as Disaster Shelters, they provided the following checklist in line with global best practices that could be adopted and domesticated in Nigeria's disaster management and mitigation efforts in schools. These checklists include:

- i. Identify potential hazards and risks through hazard assessment to determine the likelihood and severity of each hazard and develop plans accordingly.*
- ii. Create emergency plans and evacuation routes and procedures while responding to different types of disasters.*
- iii. Identify resources and equipment as well as ways to maintain needed surplus and how to track replenishing them.*

- iv. Prepare facilities and basic infrastructure, and secure them for use during a disaster while identifying some school facilities that can be used for temporary shelter.*

- v. Prepare the staff and community with regular training and education to assume roles and responsibilities during a disaster response.*

- vi. Provide effective communication and coordination, to establish clear lines of communication and coordination with local government agencies, emergency services, community organizations, and volunteers.*

- vii. Establish a clear protocol for communication and coordination with emergency services, such as police, fire, and medical personnel.*

- viii. Establish partnerships with local organizations and businesses to provide resources and support during a disaster response.*

- ix. Regularly conduct drills and exercises to test the emergency plans and procedures and identify areas for improvement.*

- x. Develop a clear communication plan for sharing information with the community during a disaster response.*

Effects of Unplanned Use of Schools as Temporary Shelters or Camps for Disaster-Displaced Victims

Across the globe, the abrupt closure of schools due to emergency situations triggered by disaster events has emerged as a major challenge, disrupting the education of millions of learners—and African nations, including Nigeria, have not been exempt from this trend. Such closures are typically initiated in response to urgent public safety concerns, particularly during health emergencies where limiting the spread of infectious diseases necessitates strict public health measures (Brooks et al., 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic, along with previous outbreaks such as the Ebola virus, serve as clear examples where lockdowns led to widespread school shutdowns. While these actions aim to safeguard public health, they also bring significant repercussions, affecting students, families, and the broader society by disrupting education and influencing both social structures

and economic stability. As a result, the topic has sparked considerable discussion among educators, parents, and decision-makers.

In Nigeria and other parts of Africa, additional factors have contributed to school closures, including both natural and human-induced disasters. In the southern regions, flooding often leads to the temporary suspension of schooling, while in the north, violence stemming from terrorism, banditry, and frequent kidnappings has severely impacted educational access. In many instances, the looming threat of attacks has compelled authorities to shut down schools as a precautionary measure to protect lives, property, and students' welfare (Tyohemba, 2022).

In all of these, there are multi-dimensional effects of this sudden and unplanned School closure on the entire school system and stakeholders. Apart from the general consequence of creating teaching and learning crises, or worsening the learning outcomes and exacerbating school dropout, most especially, in some developing countries, there are other effects peculiar to the school children and their teachers, the school academic calendar, as well as effects on the Parents or family. For this paper, therefore, these sundry effects are discussed under the following heading:

- (i) Effects on School Children
- (ii) Effects on School Teachers
- (iii) Effects on Parents and the Family
- (iv) Effects on School Academic Calendar
- (v) Cross-cutting and Socioeconomic effects

Effect on School Children

A number of surveys conducted by UNESCO, along with discussions presented at the “Why It Matters” Academic Conference on the Sustainable Development Goals Decade of Action (covering SDG 1–7), held at Utah Valley University from October 5 to 7, 2022, highlight a widespread academic agreement regarding the educational disruption caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. According to the data presented, the crisis placed millions of learners at risk of never returning to school. Approximately 24 million students across all educational levels—from pre-

primary to tertiary—were affected, with 10.9 million in primary and secondary education. Of this figure, 11.2 million were girls and young women, including 5.2 million enrolled at the primary and secondary levels (UNESCO, 2020; UVU, 2022).

An illustrative example from July 2022, reported by Tyoheba Henry in *Leadership Newspaper* under the title *Measuring The Impact of Unplanned School Closures*, revealed that over seven states in northern Nigeria shut down schools due to escalating cases of abductions and banditry. Experts warned that such developments could further increase the already alarming number of children out of school. Following these state-level closures, the federal government of Nigeria responded by ordering the immediate shutdown of several Unity Colleges in the region as a preventive security measure (Tyoheba, 2022). Comparable incidents were also recorded in Bayelsa and Delta States during 2020 and 2022, where government authorities instructed the Ministry of Education to suspend school operations due to widespread flooding, which had submerged numerous school facilities and rendered access routes impassable.

“The Bayelsa State Government has directed all Public Primary, Secondary, and Private Schools in the state to suspend all academic activities and embark on a flood break from Monday 3rd October to Friday 11th November 2022. This directive according to Daily Post(2022) became necessary to safeguard the lives of teachers and students as flood continues to submerge parts of the state.- Daily Post, October 3rd, 2022” (CEOAfrica, 2022)

Effects on School Teachers

Müller and Goldenberg (2020) highlight that during lockdowns, teachers not only experienced the same difficulties as the general public—such as balancing work with caregiving and household responsibilities—but also encountered distinct challenges tied to their professional duties in supporting students. As schools remained shut, educators were often faced with the critical task of maintaining learning continuity, which brought about extra demands, including the need to swiftly adapt to digital tools and manage heavier workloads from home. Many educators,

lacking sufficient training and clear guidance for facilitating online instruction, found themselves ill-equipped to handle these new expectations (Müller & Goldenberg, 2020). As a result, Müller and Goldenberg emphasize the pressing need for targeted professional support systems to help teachers navigate such demanding conditions and to sustain educational standards during crises.

Effects on Parent and the Family

Apart from its effects on students and their teachers, school closures also place a significant burden on families, particularly those with working parents. The sudden need for childcare can disrupt household routines and create financial strain. Additionally, parents may struggle to balance work responsibilities with supervising their children's remote learning. For many families, finding reliable childcare during school closures can be a daunting task. Single-parent households and low-income families are often the most affected, as they may lack the resources to hire professional childcare services. This situation can lead to increased stress and anxiety for both parents and children. According to Warah (2022) and a report by UNICEF (2022), During periods of school closure, girls are at increased risk of experiencing sexual abuse and exploitation due to the absence of the protective environment that educational institutions typically provide.

According to a report by Tyohemba (2022), a parent from Kwali, Nigeria—identified as Joseph—stated that the closure of schools imposes significant social and economic burdens on communities. He emphasized that these effects are especially harsh on the most disadvantaged and marginalized children and their families. “Such disruptions,” he noted, “not only deepen pre-existing inequalities in the education system but also negatively affect other areas of their lives.” Another parent, referred to as Mrs. Peace, expressed concern to journalists while collecting her child from FGC in Kwali. She regretted the interruption of her children's exams and remarked that it was safer to bring them home under the circumstances.

Effect on School Academic Calendar

One of the most immediate effects of school closures is the disruption to the smooth progress of the academic calendar. Students may fall behind in their studies, particularly in subjects that require continuous learning, such as mathematics and languages, a situation that could be made worse for students from disadvantaged homes whose parents may lack access to alternative learning resources. Students may experience learning loss due to prolonged absence from school. School closures remove a critical layer of protection for girls, leaving them more exposed to risks of sexual abuse and exploitation. As the long-term consequences of keeping students out of the classroom begin to emerge, they may include increased cases of unintended pregnancies, involvement in cult activities, unemployment among private school teachers, and broader economic instability. Furthermore, such closures significantly disrupt the academic calendar, placing students' educational progress at serious risk (Blueprint Newspaper, 2020).

While the decision to close schools was intended to protect students' health and safety, experts argue that this abrupt measure has negatively impacted children's educational development (Jacob, 2021; Tyohemba, 2022). The United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) has raised serious concerns about what it calls a 'Learning Crisis in Nigeria'. According to the agency, 70 percent of children in the country are facing substantial challenges in their education. Data from the 2021 Nigerian Literacy report shows that 53 percent of ten-year-olds are unable to read or write, underscoring the urgency and legitimacy of the learning crisis (UNICEF, 2022).

Cross-Cutting and Socioeconomic Effects

Studies have equally revealed that the economic impact of school closures extends beyond individual families. Businesses may experience reduced productivity as employees struggle to balance work and family responsibilities. Furthermore, according to the reports of World Bank-UNESCO-UNICEF report (2021), the disruption in education can have long-term effects on the workforce, potentially leading to a

decline in economic growth. Extensive research has consistently demonstrated a strong link between educational attainment and income levels. Interruptions in education and skill development among today's learners are expected to result in long-term economic consequences. Hanushek and Woessmann (2020) identify two primary channels through which school closures contribute to enduring economic costs. The first pertains to individual students, whose disrupted education due to the pandemic is likely to lead to diminished earnings over their lifetimes. The second concerns the broader economic implications, as countries with a workforce that lacks adequate skills may experience reduced economic growth, ultimately undermining societal well-being.

Recommendations and Conclusion

In times of crisis, providing shelter is a core aspect of the humanitarian mandate and essential for safeguarding lives (Sabarwal et al., 2024). Ensuring that forcibly displaced individuals have access to safe and healthy living spaces is crucial, as such environments shield them from harsh weather, and uphold their rights to privacy, dignity, comfort, and emotional well-being (UNHCR, 2024). Furthermore, Tyohemba (2022) previously emphasized that while the decision to close schools was necessary to ensure the safety of students, the abrupt nature of these closures has, according to experts, significantly hindered children's educational progress. Based on these insights, the following recommendations are proposed:

(a) Although the frequency and severity of school closures in Nigeria may not have been adequately captured, the disruption of the school system through closure will likely persist, with the possible overarching implications of learning losses and dropouts.

(b) In line with global best practices as exemplified with particular reference to Florida, Japan, and Australia. Planning and preparedness of schools to be used as temporary camps in Nigeria should henceforth attract adequate budgetary funding from the government to ensure that educational facilities are sufficiently prepared before a disaster strike.

(c) As it is required of emergency camps/shelters (in this case schools), to function as temporary camps, school facilities should henceforth be designed, constructed and equipped with building disaster-resilient school facilities to withstand the odds of IDP camps.

(d) Henceforth, comprehensive contingency plans for emergencies should be some of the key strategies for future preparedness before a disaster strikes. This should include the upscaling investment in digital infrastructure and resources for online learning, as well as enhancing teacher training and professional development programme to enable them to cope during school closure, when informal teaching and learning are expected to go on.

In conclusion, School closures present significant challenges that require a coordinated and thoughtful response. By understanding the reasons behind closures, their impact on students, teachers/staff, families, and the economic consequences as earlier presented, we need to develop effective solutions to mitigate these impacts. It has also been brought to the fore in this paper the need to embrace remote learning, supporting teachers, and implementing sound policies which are critical steps toward ensuring the continuity of education during crises when the schools would have been shut down. However desirable or suitable it may seem to be either for a temporary or a short time, the contest over the use of school facilities for different purposes aside from teaching and learning remains. Furthermore, schools that have not been specifically planned and equipped to function as evacuation centers or temporary shelters for at-risk populations should not be repurposed for such use unless comprehensive preparedness measures are implemented in advance.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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